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A Preliminary Study of Integrating Creative Strategies in an “Industry 4.0” Project-based Course

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to integrate creative strategies of “brainstorming” and the “six thinking hats” in an “industry 4.0” project-based course, in an attempt to cultivate creative climate and creativity for mechanical engineering and digital learning students. Participants were forty-three students enrolling in a project-based course. A post-survey of creative climate was conducted and students’ final projects were evaluated for creativity. Results of regression indicate that, among the eight dimensions of creative climate, “sufficient resources” and “managerial encouragement” can significantly explain 19.4% of the variance in students’ creativity ($F(8,32) = 2.200, p = .054$). The effects of “sufficient resources” on students’ creativity was very likely resulted from the creative strategies employed in the course, while the effects of “managerial encouragement” may come from creative strategies as well as the teacher’s supportive behaviors. Suggestions for future studies are provided.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Engineering Education Research, Student Cooperation

Keywords: Creative-Thinking Strategy, Creative Climate, Creativity

INTRODUCTION

In the era of the “4th industrial revolution (industry 4.0)” where the combination of the Internet and future-oriented technologies results in innovation in industrial production [1], the development of creativity, whether in family, school, organization, etc. has gradually drawn attention worldwide. Creativity is indeed one of the key 21st century skills indicated in Trilling and Fadel's study [2]. Nevertheless, college students in the Taiwanese vocational education system have long been oriented towards pursuing higher education, and there is a lack of creativity competence; students generally do not know how to design and actualize creative products independently. Creative-thinking strategies are crucial for enhancing students’ creativity. Studies have shown that teachers could utilize creative-thinking strategies for bringing out students’ potential to create [3]. At the same time, the construct of a “creative climate” is a focal point among scholars when discussing factors for inducing creativity [4]. In view of this, the design of the present study is to integrate creative strategies into an “industry 4.0” project-based course, in an attempt to promote creative climate and to further spur students’ creativity.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Creativity

Woodman et al. [5] suggest viewing creativity in social systems from the following

components: (i) creative persons, (ii) creative processes, (iii) creative situations, (iv) creative products, and (v) the interactions of these components. Creativity can be viewed as a person's innate ability to create, a thinking process that generates novel solutions to problems and original, useful products. The environment one situates in can stimulate or suppress one's creativity, and vice versa. Creativity can also result from the complex interaction of personal traits, thinking process, and environment, and it manifests in various forms such as products or concepts. Mayer [6] found that most scholars have indicated that creativity relates to new and useful products, including concepts and concrete objects, and that "product" is the desirable target of assessment if one wishes to test the substantive ability to create. Consequently, the present study evaluates students' creativity based on the products created in a project-based course.

1.2 Creative climate

When it comes to cultivating students' creativity in classroom, the learning environment is one of the most essential factors [7]. The climate of an environment, such as an organization, is conceptualized as the shared beliefs or perceptions about the contingencies, requirements, and practices of the organization [8], such as employees' perceptions on the leaders' management styles, degree of workload, relationships among colleagues, and autonomy in conducting one's work. Environmental factors spurring creativity can be further characterized as creative climate [9].

Amabile, Conti, Coon, Lazenby, and Herron [10] developed "KEYS" to assess the climate for creativity. It is implied from "KEYS" that creativity could be enhanced through socialization of the work environment. "KEYS" comprises eight dimensions: (i) *organizational encouragement* refers to an organizational culture that judges employees' ideas fairly, constructively, and supportively. It rewards and recognizes creative work and utilizes mechanisms for generating new ideas. (ii) *supervisory encouragement* refers to supervisors who set clear goals, are able to establish good working environment, serve as a work model, and show confidence in employees. (iii) *work group supports* refer to being in a group where members communicate well, open to various ideas, trust, and feel committed to their work. (iv) *freedom* indicates the autonomy and control over what work to do and how to proceed. (v) *sufficient resources* are access to sufficient resources, such as funds, materials, facilities, and information. (vi) *challenging work* indicates that people realize they should endeavor to deal with challenging works and important projects. (vii) *realistic workload pressure* are lack of excessive time pressures, unrealistic expectations for employee's productivity, or distractions from work. (viii) *lack of organizational impediments* refer to an organizational culture that lacks internal political problems, conservatism, destructive internal competition, and harsh managerial structure.

1.3 Creative-thinking strategies

The purpose of creative-thinking strategies is to increase students' creativity via customized activities [11]. In the present study, the strategies are "brainstorming" and the "six thinking hats". "Brainstorming" [12] is a method for yielding a large number of ideas that are to be processed later. The guidelines of brainstorming are: (i) Negative judgment of ideas should be deferred until later. (ii) Truly wild ideas are desired. (iii) The more ideas produced, the greater chance of yielding useful ones. (iv) Elaborating on others' ideas to produce new ones [13]. Studies have found that brainstorming can help learners organize and arrange their thoughts [14]. The other strategy, the "six thinking hats", [15] allows one to pinpoint a certain type of thinking at a time, and competence in thinking can increase by adopting appropriate thinking styles. The six thinking modes are white (objective facts), red (emotion), black (critical), yellow (optimistic), green (creative), and blue (organization). It has been supported by studies that the six thinking hats can help one conceive more original and a larger number of ideas [16].

2 RESEARCH PURPOSE AND QUESTIONS

The purpose of the present study is to integrate creative strategies into an "industry 4.0" project-based course at a college to cultivate creative climate, and to examine if students' creativity could be promoted through such strategies. Especially, the main research question is how do creative-thinking strategies influence students' creativity?

3 METHOD

3.1 Instructional contexts: Creative-thinking strategies and project-based course

Authors of the present study and the instructors who teach project courses collaborated to develop a target course for the present study that is based on a pre-existent project-based course that teaches theories and practice of "industry 4.0". The main focus of the target course is to integrate creative-thinking strategies with industry 4.0 instructions. The course contains four topics: industry 4.0 and sensors, innovation and application in web of things, cyber physical system, and application of big data and cloud in industry 4.0. The course lasted one semester (eighteen weeks), with each session lasting four hours (one-hour practice class included), six of which comprising two hours of creative thinking instructions across the whole curriculum. Students were required to yield a plan for their projects related to "industry 4.0", such as creating a smart vending machine or an autonomous vehicle. Students then had to further bring their plans into practice. They were instructed to work in groups, utilizing creative-thinking strategies by discussing topics related to "industry 4.0" and cooperatively developing final projects. For instance, brainstorming was used to

conceive how to apply web of things onto the final project. The “six thinking hats” was used to help students contemplate the contents and feasibility of the final project, as well as help them examine how big data can be applied into industry 4.0.

3.2 Participants

The participants were forty-three students who majored in mechanic engineering or digital learning at a college in Taipei city, Taiwan. They were students who took a project-based course called “Industry 4.0: Theory and Practice” in 2016.

3.3 Procedure

Assessment was conducted using James’ revised version of “KEYS” [17] to measure creative climate, where students indicated their perceptions on each dimension of the course climate. The procedure included two stages: (i) *An “industry 4.0” project-based course was carried out.* (ii) *The creative climate questionnaire was conducted at the end of the course with students’ final products being evaluated by experts.* Interviews were also carried out, where students were instructed to answer interview questions based on their experience in, perceptions on, and suggestions toward the course.

4 RESULTS

Excluding two invalid cases, there are in total forty-one effective cases for analysis. For the overall regression model, the eight dimensions of creative climate significantly explain 19.4% of the variance in creativity score ($F(8,32) = 2.200, p = .054$). We then aimed at finding which dimensions can significantly explain the creativity score, and results indicate that two dimensions have such effects. The one with a stronger effect is “sufficient resources” ($\beta = .469, p = .049$), and the other is “managerial encouragement” ($\beta = .396, p = .046$). The positive coefficients of both variables indicate that with an increase in “sufficient resources” or “managerial encouragement”, students’ creativity also increases.

Table 1. Multiple regression analysis for explaining creativity score on dimensions of creative climate

	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>B</i>	<i>Se</i>	Beta		
(constant)	55.318	10.665		5.187	.000
Freedom	1.686	3.528	.088	.478	.636
Challenging Work	-.282	2.665	-.022	-.106	.916
Managerial Encouragement	4.816	2.320	.396	2.075	.046
Work Group Supports	6.395	4.454	.512	1.436	.161
Organizational Encouragement	-5.637	4.341	-.443	-1.299	.203

Lack of Organizational Impediments	-4.291	3.848	-.278	-1.115	.273
Sufficient Resources	5.777	2.822	.469	2.047	.049
Realistic Workload Pressure	-2.199	1.842	-.230	-1.194	.241

5 DISCUSSION

The present study integrated creative-thinking strategies with a project-based course, finding that “sufficient resources” and “managerial encouragement” can predict students’ creativity performance. It is suggested that the application of creative strategies in the course may have successfully provided students with sufficient resources for tackling problems. For instance, in the interviews, many students gave credit to the “six thinking hats”; one student expressed that “the ‘six thinking hats’ allowed me to organize my ideas with structure” and that the method helped “create phrases in each category so there was something to discuss”. When students could not find essential resources at hand, they were nevertheless able to find creative ways to find replacement by using the “six thinking hats” method. Moreover, students were asked to make a list of the resources they needed for their projects during the “brainstorming” sessions, which very likely helped them know better about their resources. In addition, the requested resources, may it be tools, money, or other supplies, were provided immediately to students most of the times.

The increase of students’ creativity may also come from teacher’s encouragement. The design of the course may have encouraged the teacher to explain clearly the project goals to students, support students’ ideas, show confidence in them, and evaluate their works fairly and supportively. Furthermore, it is indicated that students did not show fear when proposing ideas, because the principles of “brainstorming” and “deferment of criticism” were emphasized by the teacher. All of the aforementioned elements of “managerial encouragement” resemble those of transformational leadership, which can increase employee creativity. This outcome is supported by the results of previous studies, such as that providing followers with confidence in them to excel at work [18], or that providing individualized consideration such as recognition and encouragement can both enhance creativity [19].

6 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, “brainstorming” and the “six thinking hats” are applied in an “Industry 4.0” project-based course to enhance students’ creativity through creative climate. It is indicated that “sufficient resources” and “managerial encouragement” have positive effects on students’ performance on creativity. It is likely that creative strategies provided participants with thinking structures, when listing and organizing their resources, for example. Meanwhile, the teacher established a good learning environment by setting clear goals, recognizing students’ contributions, and

encouraging ideas without harsh criticism. Thus, a conclusion can be drawn, that is, both mechanisms, “sufficient resources” and “managerial encouragement”, can help develop students’ creativity. Nevertheless, while the present study implies that creative strategies such as “brainstorming” and the “six thinking hats” do have positive effects, their effects manifested only in two creative climate dimensions. Thus, it is suggested that future studies employ other creative strategies to test whether they can trigger other aspects of the creative climate that can affect students’ creativity.

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